

THE IMPACT OF STRATEGIC HUMAN CAPITAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS IN MANUFACTURING INDUSTRIES

SREEDEVI. P *

Research Scholar, Management Studies, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, India.

*Corresponding Author Email: sridevip.111@gmail.com

N. KISHORE BABU

Professor, Commerce and Management Studies, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, India.

Email: dr.n.kishorebabu@gmail.com

Abstract

Strategic human capital management (SHCM) practices have great importance to create the value for the employees. The present study assesses the impact of SHCM practices on manufacturing industries in Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh, India. The main objective of this study is to assess the effect of SHCM practices on organizational effectiveness. The various key practices of SHCM include man power planning, recruitment and selection, onboarding, competency policy, coaching and mentoring, employee training, competency and career development plan and employee retention are taken to collect relevant data and to identify the outcomes based on the employee responses. A total of 600 questionnaires were distributed to the employees and 535 responses were received. Statistical package for social sciences 8.1.1, AMOS version 26 was used for data analysis and interpretation. The results state the need of implementing SHCM practices to enhance the skills of the employees and to exhibits the competencies of the organization.

Keywords: Strategic Human Capital, Organizational Effectiveness, Manufacturing Industries, Man Power Planning, Recruitment and Selection, Onboarding, Competency Policy, Coaching and Mentoring, Employee Training, Competency and Career Development Plan, Employee Retention, SCHM Practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human capital management is crucial for improving leadership competencies and has a significant impact on corporate success and societal development through organizational effectiveness (Elena A. Kamyshina, 2024). Strategic human capital management has a significant role on organizational competitiveness by aligning HR practices with business goal and ultimately leads to competitive advantage. Human capital management practices include recruitment and selection, training and development, Performance Appraisal and Career Management are essential to enhance employee skills, engagement, performance and retention (Anusuya M, 2024). Human capital resources refers to individual or corporate level capabilities relating to knowledge, skills and abilities (poyhart et al, 2014). Human capital is the added value that people provide for organizations (Baron and Armstrong, 2007). Human capital is important and it has positive relationship with business performance (Nick Bontis, 2000). Effective human capital management is crucial for sustainable organizational success and to enhance employee performance and achieve the employee goal with organizational objectives and for talent development (Escano, Jeanrose C, 2023) effective human capital management has direct influence on individual and team performance and significantly impacts on

overall business success and employees are considered as vital asset for the companies (Helena R. Costakis, 2022)

In the present competitive world human capital management has challenges include attracting talent, adopting technological changes and ensure to make the employees for continuous learning and develop employee skills to meet the workforce needs. (Lucas Mariasavery, 2020) This research aims to explore the impact of human capital management practices on organizational performance and to ensure that significant outcomes with effective strategic human capital management in manufacturing industries. The various strategic human capital management practices and its impact on organizational effectiveness is shown in the figure:1.

Figure 1: Strategic human capital management practices and its impact on organizational effectiveness

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to analyse the impact of strategic human capital management practices on organizational effectiveness in manufacturing industries and how SHCM practices are useful to overcome HCM challenges.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The important contribution by Benson honig; 2001, characteristics of human capital of micro entrepreneurs are closely related to their success of the organization. The research findings by Djilali Benabou; 2013 showed Human resources are considered as unique asset and it can provide competitive advantage. Organizations are giving importance to managing human resources due to changes in business environment when increasing globalization. The important contribution by Salwa Muda, 2016 states that human capital

has an important role in increasing small and medium enterprises (SMEs) performance directly and indirectly. SMEs need to focus on human capital attributes like education, skills and talent to have superior performance. The findings by Andre; 2015, Human capital management has goal to improve the employee performance and by the end it will increase the company's performance. According to Jun-You Lin; 2013, the divergent of Research and development in human capital is useful for industry performance with experience in diversity and interaction between competence and knowledge of the employee. Furthermore, the human capital programs can be viewed as innovation and SMEs need to focus on these programs to get benefit because of other firms may not take the similar action (Brian S. Klaas; 2010). The findings from the research by Lei Yaping; Lei Yaping human capital is very important for better results and different organizations have different characteristics of human capital so they should focus to design the human capital investment to meet the targets set by the organizations.

Another important research finding by W. Heather M. Fernando; 2020 is that industries were practicing distinctive human capital practices and the suggestion is industries need to focus on specific skills and education to improve specific skills to complete the work. Further the research findings by James C. Hayton, 2004, Human capital management plays an important role in the integration of the HR system. SMEs were having more investments in HR practices to improve participation from the employees in decision making and organizational learning and these are helpful to develop HCM capabilities and for sustained competitive advantage. Another finding by Chia-ningchia-ning chiuchiu, 2023 proved that firms are having high micro human capital have low turnover. The study by Main Naser Alolayyan, 2021 found that the practice of strategic human capital management was positively related to employee commitment and also it was helpful for human capital development. Important findings by Lee S; 2024 human capital is considered as moderator between obsessive passion of CEOs' and performance feedback. Another finding by de Faria P; 2021, the impact to hiring decisions was positively affected on domestic firms as well as MNC companies. Another research finding by knowledge sharing is very useful and act as mediation in the influence of human capital (HC) on innovation. The research finding by Abdul Muslim; 2023, strategic human capital, strategic competence and strategic partnership are greatly influence the firm performance. Another important study by Mbah Paulinus Chigozie, 2018, while evaluating the impact of human capital development was positive on organizational performance in manufacturing industries. The results showed that knowledge was positively influence on product quality and skills have positive impact on innovations. The research findings by Ajisafe, 2015, research was conducted on 12 commercial banks and found that there is a positive effect of human capital management on organizational performance. Another contribution by Wenny Desty Febrian, 2023, human capital management can create a strong organizational culture and it is useful for employee development and commitment to achieve goal of the organization. Another research by the capacity, knowledge and skills of human capital have a positive relationship with organizational performance. Human capital is considered as strategic asset and it contributes organizational effectiveness and human capital should be valuable when organizations focussed on specific educational background and specific work experience (Abraham Carmeli, 2004).

Training initiatives improves the both technical and soft skills and have a vigorous impact on performance of employee in engineering industries (Muhammad Danial Mohd Talha, 2024).

The objective of this study is to examine the link between SHCM practices and organizational effectiveness in large manufacturing companies in Kakinada. The following hypothesis were formulated for result analysis.

H1: Manpower planning has influence on organizational effectiveness

H2: There is an impact of Recruitment and selection on organizational effectiveness

H3: Onboarding has effect on organizational effectiveness

H4: Competency policy has effect on organizational effectiveness

H5: Coaching and mentoring has impact on organizational effectiveness

H6: Employee training has positive effect on organizational effectiveness

H7: Competency and career development plan has influence on organizational effectiveness

H8: Employee retention has impact on organizational effectiveness

4. METHODOLOGY

This research was based on data collected from both primary and secondary. Primary data was collected through questionnaires with 44 closed ended questions measured on Likert scale with 5 point rating from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Secondary data was collected from various books, journals. Data was collected by using convenient sampling method and stratified sampling method. Convenient sampling method was used to select manufacturing industries and stratified sampling method was applied to collect data from the employees. Large-scale manufacturing industries were selected to collect questionnaires and there are 600 questionnaires were distributed among employees and 535 responses were collected from the employees. Responses were collected from 3 manufacturing industries located in Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh. The structured questionnaire includes demographic data of the employees and various factors of strategic human capital management. The questionnaire was designed with interval scale and used 5-point Likert scale. The statistical methods include one sample kolmogov test, Cronbach alpha test, Kruskal wallis test, exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modelling were applied to study the impact of strategic human capital management practices on organizational effectiveness. SPSS, AMOS- 26 version was used to measure the data.

5. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

5.1 Summary of one sample Kolmogov test to test the normality

Independent variables like manpower planning, recruitment and selection, onboarding, coaching and mentoring, compensation planning, employee training, competency and

career development plan and employee retention were taken as strategic human capital management practices. Organizational effectiveness was taken as dependent variable. One sample Kolmogorov test was applied to test the normality of each sample of independent variable. The results shown that the p value is less than 0.005 for each independent variable. It indicates that the test distribution is normal

5.2 Test results of reliability test

Cronbach's alpha test was used to measure the internal consistency of the data. Cronbach's alpha value for manpower planning was 0.825, 0.709 for recruitment and selection, 0.641 for onboarding, 0.676 compensation policy, 0.569 for coaching and mentoring, 0.893 for employee training, 0.597 for competency and career development plan, 0.795 for employee retention. Manpower planning, recruitment and selection, employee training, employee retention were having cronbach's alpha value more than 0.07. It indicates good reliability. Onboarding, compensation policy, coaching and mentoring, competency and career development plan were having Alpha value less than 0.07 and more than 0.05. it indicates that there is acceptable reliability among the variables (Griethuijsen et al., 2014). Reliability test values are shown below.

Table 1: Reliability test

Name of the variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No of Items
Manpower planning	.825	.790	5
Recruitment and selection	.709	.721	5
Onboarding	.641	.640	5
Compensation planning	.676	.682	5
Coaching and mentoring	.569	.573	5
Employee training	.893	.892	5
Competency & career development plan	.597	.603	7
Employee retention	.795	.780	7

5.3 Summary of Kruskal wallis test

Kruskal wallis independent test was performed to know the statistical significance between independent and dependent variables. In this study the Kruskal wallis test was conducted to observe the impact of employee demographic changes on SHCM practices. The results showed that the significant relationship between employee demographics and SHRM practices. The test results of age on SHCM practices showed that the P value is less than 0.01. It clearly states that when the age of the employee increases there is high impact on SHRM practices. So it rejects the null hypothesis. When comparing of experience of the employee and SHCM practices, there is an impact of experience on SHCM practices. So it is considered that when employee experience increases there is positive impact on the SHCM practices. Based on employee salary it is observed that there is positive impact on the SHCM practices. When the test was applied on gender basis the result showed that there is no impact on SHCM practices. The test results of economic background of the employees showed that there is no impact on SHCM

practices. The result of managerial level showed that there is no impact on SHCM practices. The result of educational level of the employees showed that there is an impact on SHCM practices. So, when employees have higher education there is positive impact on SHCM practices. Finally, from Kruskal wallis test it is concluded there is positive impact of increase in age, experience, salary and education level on SHCM practices and no impact of gender, economic background, managerial level on SHCM practices.

Table 2: Result of Kruskal wallis test:

Independent variables	Dependent variable	Sig.value	Decision
SHCM practices	Age	<0.001	Reject the Null Hypothesis
SHCM practices	Experience	<0.001	Reject the Null Hypothesis
SHCM practices	Salary	<0.001	Reject the Null Hypothesis
SHCM practices	Education level	<0.001	Reject the Null Hypothesis
SHCM practices	Gender	0.505	Retain the Null Hypothesis
SHCM practices	Economic back ground	0.607	Retain the Null Hypothesis
SHCM practices	Managerial level	0.773	Retain the Null Hypothesis

5.4 Exploratory factor analysis

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed to grouping the variables. Each factor included sub factors which are framed through structured questionnaire. EFA was applied on independent variables of SHCM practices initially all the sub factors were not comes under the same group. So that some sub factors are removed which are comes under other group and again EFA was applied and varimax method was applied for rotation. Finally the result was found for 8 factors with eigen value greater than one. The EFA result is shown below.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Measure of Sampling Adequacy (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin)		.659
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Chi-Square (Approx)	18041.480
	Degree of freedom	406
	Significance	<.001

KMO measures sampling adequacy for proceeding factor analysis. Here Kaiser Value is 0.659 which indicates satisfactory i.e greater than 0.05 (Kaiser, 1974) and the Bartlett's test shown that sphericity is significant which is less than 0.05. From the EFA analysis the following result were found from Rotated component matrix shown Table no: 4. From the rotated component matrix it is observed that all the factor loadings are greater than 0.5 so all the variables could be considered for further analysis. The values of factor loadings includes Manpower planning process to meet the goal and objectives of the company (MP1) has the value 0.956, Manpower planning to recruit the required level employees (MP2) has 0.972 factor loading, Manpower planning to design development plan for the employees (MP3) has 0.561, Manpower planning in succession planning (MP5) has 0.972, Recruitment and selecting process in the company (RS1) has 0.983, Approach of the management while recruiting employees in the organization (RS4) has 0.981, Recruitment process for different grades of employees (RS5) has 0.947, Onboarding process and its impact on understanding company company's culture,

mission and vision (OB1) has 0.898, Is there standard onboarding process (OB2) has 0.899, Assistance to understand the role of employee in the company after conducting orientation program (OB4) has 0.836, Policy of the organization including flexible benefits, leave encashment policy while paying salaries to the employees (CP1) has 0.818, Compensation planning and strategy for large workforce varying with pay grades, skill levels and specialities (CP2) has 0.889, Compensation to the employees are attractive and retain the employees (CP5) has 0.675, Coaching and mentoring process to improve overall productivity of the company (CM2) has 0.731, Mentors develop strategies and help the employees to meet goal of the company (CM4) has 0.670, Mentors help to the employees to balance work with their personal life (CM5) has 0.817, Training program from the last six months and it impact on employee career goal (ET1) has 0.981, Training program to improve employee working skills (ET2) has 0.976, Training methods to enhance the quality of working (ET3) has 0.831, Conducting training programs frequently and it is relevant to the employee needs to perform their job (ET5) has 0.982, Competency management program available to HR team to collect observable skills, behaviours, and attitudes that impact the work efficiency of the employees (CCDP1) has 0.924, Competency management is good to identifying gaps and developing capabilities (CCDP2) has 0.924, Competency management to improve productivity and job satisfaction (CCDP4) has 0.713, Expectations about the progress of the employee in the organization (CCDP5) has 0.582, Suitable working conditions to the employees (ER1) has 0.922, recognition and appreciation to the hard work of the employees (ER2) has 0.911, Encouragement from the organization to learning new skills (ER3) has 0.567, Comfortness to work in the organization (ER4) has 0.927, Satisfaction level with the work culture, compensation and diversity in the organization (ER5) has 0.608 factor loadings.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix

		Component							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Manpower planning	MP1			.956					
	MP2			.972					
	MP3			.561					
	MP5			.972					
Recruitment& selection	RS1				.983				
	RS4				.981				
	RS5				.947				
Onboarding	OB1						.898		
	OB2						.899		
	OB4						.836		
Compensation planning	CP1							.818	
	CP2							.889	
	CP5							.675	
Coaching& mentoring	CM2								.731
	CM4								.670
	CM5								.817
Employee Training	ET1	.981							
	ET2	.976							
	ET3	.831							

	ET5	.982							
Competency& career development plan	CCDP1					.924			
	CCDP2					.924			
	CCDP4					.713			
	CCDP5					.582			
Employee retention	ER1		.922						
	ER2		.911						
	ER3		.567						
	ER4		.927						
	ER5		.608						

Principal Component Analysis (Extraction method)

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

5.5 Confirmatory factor analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was applied after Exploratory factor analysis. Independent factors with minimum 0.6 factor loadings were taken for CFA analysis. The following results were found. Here each independent factor met the minimum requirement of CFA analysis. Each factor loading value should be greater than 0.4 (Stevens, 2002). The normal fit index should be $>.90$ (Byrne, 1994). Here the NFI value is 0.957. It indicates good fit. CFI value should be $>.90$ (Byrne, 1994).

The result showed that CFI value is 0.969. RFI value close to 1 indicates good fit. Here the RFI value is 0.942, it indicates good fit. IFI value is 0.969. IFI value is more than 0.90, indicates good fit. The result of PNFI value is 0.714 which indicates good fit. RMSEA value is 0.066 which is $<.08$ (Awang, 2012). Here the result of RMSEA value states that it is a good fit. From the output it is observed that there are 8 factors with three sub factors each. Factor one i.e.

Manpower planning (MP) has three sub factors includes Manpower planning process to meet the objectives (MP01) with factor loading of 0.97, Manpower planning to recruit the required level employees (MP02) with factor loading of 1.00, Manpower planning help to succession planning (MP05) with factor loading of 0.99 and all indicates good factor loadings.

Second factor is Recruitment and selection has sub factors includes Recruitment and selecting process (RS01) with factor loading of 1.00, Approach of the management in recruitment process (RS04) with factor loading 0.99, Recruitment process for different grades of employees (RS05) with factor loading of 0.90.

All loadings under Recruitment and selection (RS) are good. Third factor Onboarding (OB) has three sub factors includes Onboarding process to understand company's culture, mission and vision (OB1) has 0.85 factor loading, Standard onboarding process (OB2) has 0.88 factor loading and Effectiveness of orientation program (OB4) has 0.72 factor loading and all indicates good factor loadings. The model fit summary of CFA analysis is shown below

Table 5: CFA model fit summary

Test indices	Test standard	Actual Result	Resulting fit
CMIN/DF	≤ 5 (Marsh & Hocevar, 1985)	3.361	Good fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.066	Good fit
CFI	≥ 0.90 (Fan, Thompson, Wang, 1999)	0.969	Good fit
TLI	≥ 0.9 (Byrne, 1994)	0.958	Good fit
NFI	Values close to 1 (Bentler & Bonett, 1980)	0.957	Good fit
P value	p ≥ 0,05 (Joreskog & Surbom, 1996)	0.00	Good fit
RFI	A cutoff of 0.90 (Kline, 2011)	0.942	Good fit
IFI	≥ 0,90 (Bentler, 1990; Hu & Bentler, 1999)	0.969	Good fit
TLI	≥ 0,9 (Brown, 2006)	0.958	Good fit
PNFI	≥ 0.5 (Hu & Bentler, 1999)	0.714	Good fit
PCFI	≥ 0.6 (Hu & Bentler, 1999)	0.723	Good fit
NCP	<2 (Kline, 2011)	528.89	Good fit

Figure 2: The output diagram of Confirmatory factor analysis

Fourth factor Compensation policy has sub factors includes Pay policy has factor loadings (CP01) has 0.66, Compensation planning for different grade employees (CP02) has 0.99, Compensation policy to retain employees (CP05) has 0.44 factor loadings. All loadings are fit for the factor, CP02 has good factor loading comparing to others. Fifth factor that is Compensation policy (CM) has three sub factors includes Impact of coaching and mentoring process on productivity (CM02) with factor loading of 0.61, Impact of mentors to meet the goal of the company (CM04) has 0.46, Impact of mentors to balance work with personal life (CM05) has factor loading with 0.75 and all indicates fit for the analysis.

The sixth factor is Employee training has three sub factors includes factor loadings of Impact of training program to achieve career goal (ET01) with 1.00, Impact of training program to improve working skills (ET02) with 0.99, Frequency of conducting training programs (ET05) with 0.99 and all indicates good fit for the model. The seventh factor Competency and career development plan (CCDP) has three sub factors with factor loadings includes Impact of competency management program on work efficiency (CCDP01) with 1.00, Competency management plan to identifying gaps and developing capabilities (CCDP02) with 0.99, Impact of competency management on productivity and job satisfaction (CCDP04) with 0.49.

The eighth factor is Employee retention (ER) has three sub factors includes Suitable working conditions (ER01) has 0.92, Recognition of hard work of the employees (ER02) has 0.91, Comfortability to work in the organization (ER05) has 0.95 factor loadings and all are good fit the analysis. The result showed that P value is significant for all the variables under SHCM practices which is less than 0.005, so that it is concluded that null hypothesis is rejected and there is a significant relationship among SHCM practices.

5.6 Structural equation modelling

Structural equation modelling (SEM) is applied to understand the association between latent and observed variables. After CFA analysis SEM was applied for further analysis. The output result is shown below. The results states that all the values under CMIN, RMSEA, CFI, TLI, NFI, P value, RFI, IFI, TLI, PNFI, PCFI, NCP are indicates good fit.

Table 6: SEM output analysis

Acronym	Test standard	Actual Result	Resulting fit
CMIN/DF	≤ 5 (Marsh & Hocevar, 1985)	4.46	Reasonable fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.08	Acceptable fit
CFI	≥0.90 (Fan,Thompson,Wang, 1999)	0.93	Acceptable fit
TLI	≥ 0.9 (Byrne,1994)	0.91	Reasonable fit
NFI	Values close to 1 (Bentler & Bonett, 1980)	0.91	Good fit
P value	p ≥ 0,05 (Joreskog & Surbom, 1996)	0.00	Acceptable fit
RFI	A cutoff of 0.90 (Kline, 2011)	0.89	Acceptable fit
IFI	≥ 0,90 (Bentler, 1990; Hu & Bentler, 1999)	0.93	Good model fit
TLI	≥ 0,9 (Brown, 2006)	0.91	Acceptable fit
PNFI	≥ 0.5 (Hu & Bentler, 1999)	0.74	Acceptable fit
PCFI	≥ 0.6 (Hu & Bentler, 1999)	0.75	Acceptable fit
NCP	<2 (Kline, 2011)	1484.59	Acceptable fit

The output diagram of SEM analysis is represented below. From the output it is observed that all the factors are have good factor loadings except impact of onboarding on organizational effectiveness (OBOE) has 0.33, impact of employee training on organizational effectiveness (ETOE) has 0.32, impact of competency and career development plan (CCDPOE) has 0.24 All the remaining factor loadings are good which are more than 0.7. Factor loadings include Manpower planning on organizational effectiveness (MPOE, 0.98), Recruitment and selection on organizational effectiveness (RSOE, 0.86), Compensation planning on organizational effectiveness (CPOE, 0.85), Coaching and mentoring on organizational effectiveness (CMOE, 0.72) and Employee retention on organizational effectiveness (EROE, 0.98) with the latent variable Organizational effectiveness (OE). According to Field (2005) at least 4 items must be greater than 0.6, here 5 factors under organizational effectiveness have values more than 0.6. So, the output diagram is considered good fit for the analysis

Figure 3: The output diagram of Structural equation modelling

The result of significance of observed variables with latent variable showed that there are three variables have significant relationship with organizational effectiveness. From the

results, CFA analysis states that there is a relationship among SHCM practices. The SEM results showed the association between observed and latent variables. The study assessed the impact of Manpower planning (MP) on Organizational effectiveness (OE) was positive and insignificant ($b=0.80$, $t=1.872$ and $p=.061$ which is more than 0.05), hence the relation is insignificant.

Impact of Recruitment and selection (RS) on Organizational effectiveness (OE) was considered positive and significant ($b=0.106$, $t=2.502$, $p=0.012$), Impact of Onboarding (OB) on Organizational effectiveness (OE) was considered negative and insignificant ($b=-0.084$, $t=-1.854$, $p=0.064$), Impact of Compensation planning (CP) on Organizational effectiveness (OE) was positive and insignificant ($b=-0.026$, $t=-0.604$, $p=0.546$), Impact of Coaching and mentoring (CM) on Organizational effectiveness (OE) was negative and insignificant ($b=-0.051$, $t=-0.939$, $p=0.348$), Impact of Employee training (ET) on Organizational effectiveness (OE) was positive and significant ($b= 0.131$, $t= 3.111$, $p=0.002$), Impact of Competency and career development plan (CCDP) on Organizational effectiveness (OE) was negative and insignificant ($b= -0.018$, $t= -0.419$, $p= 0.675$), Impact of Employee retention (ER) on Organizational effectiveness (OE) was considered positive and significant ($b= 0.142$, $t= 3.180$, $p= 0.001$).

The result showed that the effect of Organizational effectiveness on SHCM practices was 0.78, it means there is 80% effect on SHCM practices (MP, RS, OB, CP, CM, ET, CCDP, ER) Hypothesis results are presented in Table 6.

Table 7: Results of the Hypothesis

Parameter	Standardised estimates	T value	P value	Decision
MP←OE	0.80	1.872	0.061	H1 was rejected
RS←OE	0.106	2.502	0.012	H2 was accepted
OB←OE	-0.084	-1.854	0.064	H3 was rejected
CP←OE	0.026	0.604	0.546	H4 was rejected
CM←OE	-0.051	-0.939	0.348	H5 was rejected
ET←OE	0.131	3.111	0.002	H6 was accepted
CCDP←OE	-0.018	-0.419	0.675	H7 was rejected
ER←OE	0.142	3.180	0.001	H8 was accepted

6. DISCUSSION

SHCM is the essential backbone of all human resource related initiatives. It is a people focussed approach to HR that unites process from recruitment to performance management. The various SHCM practices like Manpower planning, recruitment and selection, onboarding, compensation planning, coaching and mentoring, employee training, competency and career development plan and employee retention.

The success and survival of the organization is depends up on effective implementation of HCM practices due to high competition in the market. Based on the findings presented on Table 6 showed that there is an influence of Recruitment and selection, Employee training and Employee retention on organizational effectiveness.

Previous studies linking HRM activities with firm performance (Arthur, 1994; Huselid, 1995) proved that there is a link between HRM activities and firm performance. The result of the studies (Bhattacharya, Gibson & Doty, 2005) proved the positive relationship of human resource practices with organizational performance. Human capital increases the creative performance of employees and helps to achieve the overall goal of organization according to study of Ajisafe, Olatunbosun Emmanuel Orifa, Ruth Aina Oluwayemisi Balogun Justinah Abosede, 2015.

The study of Nick Bontis, 2007 proved that HCM practices are considered as key moderator variable and both job satisfaction and training and development (T&D) have a positive effect on employee capabilities. The study by Anita Maharani; 2020, Recruitment and training and development are influencing factors on employee performance. Companies can achieve goals optimally by giving effective training to the employees (Wenny Desty Febrian, 2023). So the hypothesis H6 was accepted. The study by Ghulam Muhammad (2022) talent attraction will be mediator between e recruitment creativity and efficiency of HCM.

The study by Pshdar Abdalla Hamza 2021, the researchers found that the selection methods used by tele communication are important. So, it is considered there is a positive influence of recruitment and selection on organizational performance. So hypothesis H2 was accepted. According to the research by Inakshi Kapoor and Pallavi tyagi, 2023, the role of human capital development was positively significant in the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and employee retention. The research findings by Xuelin Chen, 2023 employees who have experience in well-being are more likely to remain in their current roles and employee retention was important to achievement of organizational goals. So the hypothesis H8 was accepted.

7. CONCLUSION, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Our study considered there is a high impact of Recruitment and selection, Employee training and Employee retention on organizational effectiveness in manufacturing industries. SHCM practices are essential for organizational effectiveness. The result showed that, all SHCM factors have 80% of influence on organizational effectiveness. SHCM practices have a significant positive relationship on organizational effectiveness. So, it is considered effective human capital management is crucial for organizational success.

This study concluded strategic human capital management practices plays vital role for improvement of organizational effectiveness. The study is limited to manufacturing industries in Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh, India. So, it is considered research findings were gathered only from manufacturing industries in Kakinada. The present research was applied on manufacturing industries only. There is a more scope to conduct research on effect of strategic human capital management practices on other sectors like service industries and public sectors.

References

- 1) Elena A. Kamyshina, 2024. "The Importance of Human Capital in the Life of a Corporation: the Influence of Managers on the Dynamics of the Social Environment", DISCOURSE, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 66–74., <http://doi.org/10.32603/2412-8562-2024-10-3-66-74>
- 2) Anusuya M, Soundarapandian M, 2024. Exploring human capital management practices: A comprehensive review, *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 2024, 21(03), 2343–2348, <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.3.0975>
- 3) Vasyl Hoichuk, Nadiya Lyubomudrova 2024. The impact of strategic human capital management on the competitiveness of an enterprise, *Three seas economic journal*, <https://doi.org/10.30525/2661-5150/2024-2-1>
- 4) Escano, Jeanrose C, Limos-Galay, Jenny A, 2023. Human capital management in the modern workplace: Challenges and strategies for management accountants, *International Journal of Research Studies in Management* 2023 Volume 11 Number 12, 33-39, <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrsm.2023.1149>
- 5) Helena R. Costakis, Jay S. Pickern, 2022. Managing Human Capital Through the Use of Performance Improvement Plans, *Journal of Applied Business and Economics* Vol. 24(6), <https://doi.org/10.33423/jabe.v24i6.5749>
- 6) Lucas Mariasavery, S. Rajamohan, 2020. Contemporary Human Capital Issues and Challenges at Modern Workplace Conceptual Frame Work: A study, *International Journal of Humanities, Management and Social Sciences | Volume. 3 | Issue. 2 | 68-78*, <https://doi.org/10.36079/lamintang.ij-humass-0302.142>
- 7) BENSON HONIG (2001). Human capital and structural upheaval: A study of manufacturing firms in the west bank. *Journal of Business Venturing* 16, 575–594, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026\(99\)00060-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0883-9026(99)00060-9)
- 8) Dr. Djilali Benabou, Dr. Habib Tabeti: (2013), The role of strategic human capital management in achieving the competitive advantage, *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, ISSN 2281-3993, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5901/ajis.2013.v2n3p361>
- 9) Nick Bontis, William Chua Chong Keow, Stanley Richardson, 2000. Intellectual capital and business performance in Malasian industries, *Journal of intellectual capital*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691930010324188>
- 10) Salwa Muda, Mara Ridhuan Che Abdul Rahman, (2016). Human Capital in SMEs Life Cycle Perspective, *Procedia Economics and Finance* 35 (2016) 683 – 689, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(16\)00084-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(16)00084-8)
- 11) Andre, Donald Crestofel Lantu, 2015. Servant leadership and human capital management: case study in Citibank Indonesia. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 169 (2015) 303 – 311, DOI: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.314
- 12) Jun-You Lin, 2013. Effects on diversity of R&D sources and human capital on industrial performance. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2013.08.010>
- 13) Brian S. Klaas, Malayka Klimchak, Matthew Semadeni b, Jeanne Johnson Holmes, 2010. The adoption of human capital services by small and medium enterprises: A diffusion of innovative perspective. *Journal of Business Venturing* 25 (2010) 349–360, DOI: 10.1016/j.jbusvent.2008.12.002
- 14) Lei Yaping, Jia Jingfang, (2007). Human capital investment for firm: An analysis. *Management Science and Engineering* Vol.1 No.2 2007 29-35, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3968/j.mse.1913035X20070102.004>
- 15) W. Heather M. Fernando, Siti Khalidah Md Yusoff, Ali Khatibi, S. M. Ferdous Azam, S. R. S. N. Sudasinghe 2020. Human capital practices impact on organizational performance, *European journal of human resource management*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3781297>

- 16) James C. Hayton, 2004. Strategic human capital management in SMEs: an empirical study of entrepreneurial performance. *Human Resource Management*, Winter (2003). Vol. 42, No. 4, Pp. 375-391 © 2004 Wiley Periodicals, Inc. Published online in Wiley InterScience,
- 17) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/hrm.10096>
- 18) Li Ma, Xin Zhai, Weiguo Zhong, Zhi-Xue Zhang, (2018). Deploying Human Capital for Innovation: A Study of Multi-Country Manufacturing Firms, *International Journal of Production Economics*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2018.12.001>
- 19) Chia-ningchia-ning chiuchiu, (2023). Human capital be transferred efficiently? Evidence from the F&B companies, *Journal of organizational change management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOCM-06-2022-0187>
- 20) Main Naser Alolayyan, Mohammad Sharif Alyahya and Dana Ahmad Omari (2021). Strategic human resource management practices and human capital development: The role of employee commitment. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 19(2), 157-169. [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.19\(2\).2021.13](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.19(2).2021.13)
- 21) Lee S, Lee Y, Park KM (2024) Performance feedback and obsessive passion: The moderating role of human capital. *PLoS ONE* 19(4): e0302180. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0302180>
- 22) de Faria P, Schubert T, Sofka W (2021) Recruiting strategic human capital from MNCs— Does hiring MNC managers enable exporting in domestic firms? *PLoS ONE* 16(10): e0257922. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257922>
- 23) Ida Ketut Kusumawijaya, Partiw Dwi Astuti, 2023. The effect of human capital on innovation: The mediation role of knowledge creation and knowledge sharing in small companies. , 64-75. [https://doi:10.21511/kpm.07\(1\).2023.05](https://doi:10.21511/kpm.07(1).2023.05)
- 24) Bontis, N., & Serenko, A. (2007). The moderating role of human capital management practices on employee capabilities. *Journal of knowledge management*, 11(3), 31- 51.
- 25) Chigozie, M. P., AGA, C. C., & Onyia, E. (2018). Effect of Human Capital Development in Organizational Performance in Manufacturing Industries in South-East Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Economics and Management Sciences*, 7(3), 60–78, <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJAREMS/v7-i3/4378>
- 26) Muhammad Danial Mohd Talha1Norhasni Zainal Abiddin (2024). Enhancing work performance through human capital development in engineering industry: a systematic literature review, *Revista De Gestao Social E Ambiental*, <https://doi.org/10.24857/rgsa.v18n6-130>
- 27) Abraham Carmeli (2004). Strategic human capital and the performance of public sector organizations, *Scandinavian journal of management*, volume 20, Issue 4, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scaman.2003.11.003>
- 28) Abdul Muslim, Farida Jasfar , Lucy Warsindah, (2023). The effect of strategic human capital, strategic partnership, and strategic competence on firm performance in public accounting office mediated by strategic change management, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/0958519032000057781>
- 29) Ajisafe, Olatunbosun Emmanuel Orifa, Ruth Aina Oluwayemisi Balogun Justinah Abosede, 2015. Influence of Human Capital Management on Organizational Performance, *Journal of Resources Development and Management*, Vol.14.
- 30) Wenny Desty Febrian, Anggia Rettrisunz Pim Panjaitan, Kamsariaty, Josua Panatap Soehaditama, & Supardi. (2023). Human Capital Strategic: Organization Commitment, Training Need Analysis, Development People, Individual Development Plan, and Performance Appraisal. *International Journal of Integrative Sciences*, 2(4), 443–456. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijis.v2i4.3636>

- 31) Aman-Ullah, A., Mehmood, W., Amin, S., & Abbas, Y. A. (2022). Human capital and organizational performance: A moderation study through innovative leadership. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 7(4), 100261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2022.100261>
- 32) Ghulam Muhammad, Mubashara Siddique, Abdul Samad Dahri (2022) Innovative e-recruitment strategies as a tool for human capital management effectiveness: a mediating role of talent attraction. *Middle East journal of management*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/mejm.2022.125295>
- 33) Pshdar Abdalla Hamza , Baban Jabbar Othman , Bayar Gardi , Sarhang Sorguli , Hassan Mahmood Aziz , Shahla Ali Ahmed , Bawan Yassin Sabir , Nechirwan Burhan Ismael , Bayad Jamal Ali , Govand Anwar (2021) Recruitment and Selection: The Relationship between Recruitment and Selection with Organizational Performance. *International journal of Engineering, Business and Management (IJEEM)*, <https://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijeem.5.3.1>
- 34) Inakshi Kapoor and Pallavi tyagi, (2023). Entrepreneurial orientation driven employee retention: mediating role of human capital development, *Development and learning in organizations*, Vol. 37 No. 5, pp. 8-10. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLO-08-2022-0158>
- 35) Anita Maharani¹, Didi Juliansyah , Roni Putra Sanjaya, 2020. Human Capital Management Policy Effect on Employee Performance, *Jurnal Nusantara Aplikasi Manajemen Bisnis* Vol. 5 No.2 Tahun 2020, <https://doi.org/10.29407/nusamba.v5i2.14487>
- 36) Xuelin Chen, Abdullah Al Mamun, Mohammad Enamul Hoque, Wan Mohd Hirwani Wan Hussain, Qing Yang , 2023. Work design, employee well-being, and retention intention: A case study of China's young workforce, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e15742>